

THE THEME OF HOME, FAMILY IN M. BULGAKOV'S NOVELS "THE WHITE GUARD" AND "THE MASTER AND MARGARITA"

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Annotation

The article traces the evolution of the image of the house in the works of M. Bulgakov of the 30s in the context of the problem of distortion of the ideal of human existence in the post-revolutionary world. Home is a symbol of history, identity and belonging, uniting people around shared values and views of the world.

Keywords: image of home, "cross-cutting" theme, archetype, Home-world, "anti-home", moral, spiritual and cultural values, ideal model of the world order.

Among the numerous "cross-cutting" themes of Russian literature, the theme of home, family, and clan is important. This topic was addressed in their work by: A.S. Pushkin, S.T. Aksakov, L.N. Tolstoy, M. Sholokhov, F. Abramov, M. Bulgakov and others.

Home is one of the fundamental archetypes in human culture. Its primary function is to provide protection and shelter from the elements. The additional semantic load that a house acquires turns it into a symbolic model of the universe and human existence.

The image of a house plays an important role in the artistic world of Mikhail Bulgakov. The study of this image allows us to reveal the ontological problematics of his work and trace the writer's attempt to restore the lost ideal of human existence through the archetype of the house, traditional for Russian culture. The spiritual content of the house archetype echoes its idea of the world and man.

Yu.M.Lotman wrote: "History passes through a person's House, through his private life... the "independence of a person" turns him into a historical figure." [2, p. 4].

The image of a historical catastrophe is included in the novel "The White Guard" literally from the very first phrases, from the epigraphs that precede it, setting the scale and coordinates of the content and action. These coordinates will be the fate of the Turbin family, which, on the one hand, was the theme of a traditional family novel, but this fate will not only be shown against the backdrop of a historical catastrophe, but will itself become a form of

manifestation of this catastrophe. On the other hand, the historical events in the novel will be given a mysterious character, that is, behind the concrete historical plan the plan of eternity will shine through. This principle of depicting events will constitute the genre feature of this work by Bulgakov, turning a traditional novel into a mystery novel, or, as M. Petrovsky writes: "Mikhail Bulgakov's genre is not a historical tragedy, but a world mystery. He places the action of his novel in the Eternal City, for everything that happens in the Eternal City, naturally, is involved in eternity, that is, mysterious" [4, p. 11].

Historical time and the events taking place, great, close in scale to the biblical ones, are already comprehended by the author in the first sentence of the work: "Great and terrible was the year after the birth of Christ 1918, from the beginning of the second revolution." The Turbin family becomes the focus around which the key problems and features of the time are concentrated. Their existence is divided into two stages: before and after the revolution. The death of the head of the family, the mother, also occurred in the terrible year of the first revolution. This coincidence of family and historical catastrophes becomes an omen of future sad events.

For Bulgakov, the Turbins' house becomes a symbol of protection and salvation, "a ship in a terrible sea of disasters," preserving the enduring values and spiritual integrity of the family. Bulgakov emphasizes the antiquity, traditions and habitability of the house, creating an atmosphere saturated with childhood memories and strengthened by the habits characteristic of the Turbin family.

The description of the house and its furnishings conveys a sense of time that flows according to special laws in this place. Using interior details, Bulgakov creates an image of an old, cozy and kind environment, where every object and every detail has its own history and is connected with the past. This emphasizes the long-established way of life in the Turbin family and their attachment to their roots and traditions. is an important element that emphasizes the central importance of this item in the interior and symbolic significance for the Turbin family.

The stove is a symbol of comfort, prosperity and the inviolability of family traditions. The tiles on the stove serve as guardians of family history. The inscriptions made on them by the children's hands of the little Turbins, guests of the house and gentlemen in love with Elena become a kind of

“album” or chronicle that allows you to “read” the history of the family, their joys, sorrows, relationships and events.

An important item in Turbino’s domestic world is the clock: “bronze, with gavotte” - in the mother’s bedroom, “black wall” with a tower strike - in the dining room. The symbolism of watches is one of the most “talking” in world art. In Bulgakov, it takes on new meanings: if in the period before the start of the revolution, clocks playing their music were a sign of habitability, movement, seething life within these walls, now, after the death of their father and mother, their hands are counting down the last hours of a beautiful, but fading former life. But the author does not believe in the possibility of the death of this house. And even in the style of this fragment, in the use of repetitions (the refrain is “beaten with a tower fight”), he asserts eternity, the inviolability of both material symbols (a clock and a bronze lamp) and spiritual ones.

The dishonest and two-faced Talberg leaves this house “at a rat’s pace”, and the Turbins’ friends heal their wounded bodies and souls in it. And even those who, like the chairman of the house committee - the opportunist and coward Lisovich, nicknamed “Vasilisa,” hate the residents of the house, seek protection from robbers in him.

The Turbins' house is depicted in the novel as a fortress that is under siege, but does not surrender. Moreover, his image is given a high, almost philosophical meaning. According to Alexei Turbin, home is the highest value of existence, for the sake of which a person “fights and, in essence, speaking, should not fight for anything else.” To protect “human peace and hearth” - this is what he sees as the only goal that allows him to take up arms. In the Turbins’ house, “the tablecloth, despite the guns and all this languor, anxiety and nonsense, is white and starched... The floors are shiny, and in December on the table in a matte vase there are blue hydrangeas and two gloomy and sultry roses, affirming the beauty and strength of life” . This is the House in which traditions were kept, a tired soul is drawn to it.

A house, according to Bulgakov, is not walls and ceilings, not just things, customs and home holidays. These are, first of all, the people who inhabit it. Brothers Alexey and Nikolka live amicably with their sister. They are hospitable, generous, selfless. They are responsive to the pain of others, ready to take a blow intended for another, close person.

Thus, the House in the novel “The White Guard” represents both everyday reality, and a metaphor, and a symbol. This is a House-world, based

on traditional and unshakable moral, spiritual and cultural values that act as life guidelines in the Turbino world. [5, p. 68]

In the novel "The Master and Margarita" the theme of home plays an important role and is intertwined with the theme of moral "homelessness" and loneliness. Various characters go through an evolution in their relationship to home, from "anti-home" to real home, symbolizing their inner transformation and search for peace of mind. [5, p. 68].

The main character of the novel, the Master, begins his journey in the "anti-house" - in the basement room, where he lives alone and suffers from creative and moral depression. However, his meeting with Margarita becomes a turning point in his life. Margarita represents for the Master not only love and support, but also a path to understanding and accepting his past. She helps him overcome loneliness and find inner peace.

During the plot of the novel, the Master and Margarita face various obstacles and trials, but in the end they find their real home - the "eternal Home", which symbolizes spiritual well-being, harmony and peace. This home becomes for them a place where they can find refuge from the outside world and enjoy spiritual freedom.

The house, as a key image in the novel, undergoes serious transformations - a model of an "anti-house" is created, and the image of a "bad apartment" is modeled.

For the first time, the word "apartment" appears in the novel in a very ominous context: having already predicted the death of Berlioz, Woland answered the question: "And... where will you live?" - answers: "In your apartment." [1, p. 33].

This theme is developed in the words of Koroviev to Nikanor Ivanovich: "After all, he doesn't care, he's dead <...> now, you yourself agree, Nikanor Ivanovich, this apartment is of no use to him?" Berlioz's uncle appears in Moscow with the goal of "registering in the three rooms of his late nephew." The death of his nephew is an episode in solving the housing problem: "The telegram shocked Maximilian Andreevich. It was a moment that would be a shame to miss. Business people know that moments like this don't happen again." [1, p. 133]. The death of a relative is a favorable moment that should not be missed. The apartment becomes the center of the anomalous world.

The signs that separate an "anti-home" from a home cannot be reduced only to the unkemptness, neglect and homelessness of communal apartments. "Margarita Nikolaevna did not know the horrors of living in a shared

apartment,” but she also feels that it is impossible to live in a “mansion” - you can only die. Pontius Pilate equally hates Herod's palace - he lives, eats and sleeps under the columns of the balcony, unable, even during a hurricane, to enter the palace (“I cannot spend the night in it”). Only once in the novel did Pilate enter the palace - “the procurator, in a room shaded from the sun by dark curtains, had a meeting with some man whose face was half covered by a hood.” The rooms are not used for housing, but for a meeting with the head of the secret guard. The apartment becomes synonymous with something dark and, above all, denunciation. The thirst for an apartment was the reason for Aloysius Mogarych’s denunciation of the master:

“- Mogarych? - Azazello asked the one who fell from the sky.

“Aloysius Mogarych,” he answered, trembling.

- It was you who, having read Latunsky’s article about this man’s novel, wrote a complaint against him with a message that he kept illegal literature? - asked Azazello.

The new citizen turned blue and burst into tears of remorse.

- Did you want to move into his rooms? “Azazello said as sincerely as possible.” [1, p. 197].

In Bulgakov's novel, the “housing issue” becomes a metaphor and symbol of moral and spiritual decay. Throughout the novel, the writer contrasts the House with the present with various “anti-houses”: communal apartments, Griboyedov’s house, an insane asylum, Variety. The Master's story begins with his winning the lottery in the amount of one hundred thousand rubles. This event becomes a turning point when the Master decides to leave his room on Myasnitskaya Street and rents two rooms in the basement of a small house in the kindergarten. The first room, which he describes as a “huge room,” becomes his personal space, where he is surrounded by books that play an important role in his creative journey and search for truth. The second room with a sink and stove becomes a symbol of comfort and warmth, where the Master finds physical and spiritual solace.

In a new home - an “apartment” - the Master finds freedom for his creativity and begins to write his novel about Pontius Pilate. The fire in his stove symbolizes his passion and inspiration, which fuels his creative process. Working on a novel transforms a modest basement apartment into a symbolic home full of poetic meaning. As soon as the master gave up creativity, the House turned into a miserable basement: “...they broke me, I’m bored, and I want to go to the basement.”

Wolands summarizes: “So, the man who composed the story of Pontius Pilate goes into the basement with the intention of sitting there by the lamp and begging?” But the master still gets the house. Flight, leaving the world of apartments, is an important motif in the novel. Through purification by flight, the Master reaches a state of spiritual insight and finds a world where he can live in harmony with himself and the values around him.

In the novel "The Master and Margarita" there are heroes who see falsehood and hypocrisy in the world around them and have inner freedom, despite "homelessness" and the lack of spirituality in society. And this is not only the Master. With his departure, the hero's ideas do not die, but live in his follower. For the Master, this is Ivan Bezdomny, who at the beginning of the novel has a symbolic surname: it speaks of the restlessness of his soul, the lack of his own outlook on life, and ignorance.

By the end of the novel, from the poet Bezdomny, Ivan turns into a professor of history, Ivan Nikolaevich Ponyrev. Having gone through a difficult path, Ivan gains the main thing: faith and the desire for spiritual depth, for true morality, and therefore Home in the broadest sense of the word.

Yu.M. Lotman, in the article “The House in The Master and Margarita,” writes: “Bulgakov makes the House the center of spirituality, which finds expression in the wealth of internal culture, creativity and love.” [3, p. 748.]

Finding this Home means finding yourself, the opportunity to create and love, and improve spiritually. A true home, and not an “anti-home” - this is not only a specific space, but also a Home in a philosophical sense - this is the Home of the soul, its peace and freedom, which positive heroes strive to find.

Thus, the House as an ideal model of the world order is in M. Bulgakov's prose the key to a person's full spiritual life, the creative realization of the individual. The apartment becomes the opposite of the house, it carries destruction, chaos, death.

In general, the work of M. Bulgakov reflects the tendency towards the destruction of the traditional norm of existence and the ideal image of home.

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